

Effectiveness of Leg Maneuver Exercises on Orthostatic Hypotension among post operative patients admitted at selected hospitals

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ABSTRACT

Globally, the number of surgical procedures conducted has significantly increased and is still rising annually; in 2024, there were 137.5 million surgeries in India, and 110 million surgeries increasing worldwide. Enhanced recovery after surgery (ERAS) programs, sometimes referred to as fast-track surgery, are multimodal postoperative initiatives designed to reduce postoperative problems, shorten hospital stays, and speed up recovery. Epidural anaesthesia, early mobilization, early enteral feeding, and early catheter removal are all part of postoperative care. Orthostatic hypotension (OH) during postoperative care is one of the prevalent problems that can be prevented by early mobilization. Orthostatic hypotension, also known as postural hypotension, is defined as a sudden drop in blood pressure that occurs upon standing from a sitting or supine position. This condition significantly impacts quality of life and increases the risk of falls, cardiovascular disease, dementia, depression, and mortality. Clinically, orthostatic hypotension is defined as a sustained drop in systolic blood pressure (SBP) of at least 20 mm Hg or diastolic blood pressure of 10 mm Hg within 3 minutes of standing after being supine for at least 5 minutes. This sudden drop in blood pressure is typically caused by autonomic reflex failure, volume depletion, cardiovascular disease, neuropathy, or adverse medication effects. The non-pharmacologic strategy aims to minimize heat, postprandial induced vasodilation, postural venous pooling and maximize blood volume. Promoting physical conditioning, by decreasing peripheral capacitance and increasing total peripheral resistance. Leg Maneuver Exercises that primarily involve leg elevation, leg crossing, thigh muscle contraction, are used in conjunction with the majority of non-pharmacologic measures to increase venous return. The study adopted a quantitative approach with a quasi-experimental, non-randomized control group design. A sample of 30 patients selected using non-probability purposive sampling from selected hospitals. The accessible population selected for this study consisted of patients with orthostatic hypotension and those who were available during the study at selected hospitals. The effectiveness of the intervention was significantly higher in the experimental group compared to the control group. The mean reduction in orthostatic hypotension score was greater in the experimental group (16.6) than in the control group (5.3), and this difference was statistically significant (independent $t = 15.1$, $p < 0.05$). Post-intervention, 80% of patients in the experimental group had no orthostatic hypotension, whereas the majority in the control group continued to have moderate symptoms. These findings indicate that leg maneuver exercises were significantly more effective than routine care in reducing orthostatic hypotension among post-operative patients. The study established the Leg Maneuver Exercises positive impact on Orthostatic hypotension among post-operative patients. The findings emphasize the importance of targeted interventions in enhancing Orthostatic hypotension among post-operative patients. This research contributes to our understanding of the effectiveness of Leg Maneuver Exercises on Orthostatic hypotension among post-operative patients admitted at selected hospitals.

KEYWORDS: *Leg Maneuver Exercises, Orthostatic hypotension.*

INTRODUCTION

Orthostatic hypotension (OH) during postoperative care is one of the prevalent problems that can be prevented by early mobilization. However, extended immobility is a common risk for postoperative patients. Neuromuscular weakness, atelectasis, insulin resistance, joint contractures, and Orthostatic hypotension (OH) are all significantly influenced by immobility. Postoperative complications continue to be significant clinical issues in abdominal surgery.

Early patient mobilization following surgery is now common and regarded as a key strategy for reducing length of hospital stay and preventing post-operative morbidity. Orthostatic hypotension, also known as postural hypotension, is defined as a sudden drop in blood pressure that occurs upon standing from a sitting or supine position. This condition significantly impacts quality of life and increases the risk of falls, cardiovascular disease, dementia, depression, and mortality.

National data indicates that in the financial year 2019, India had total and major surgical rates of 1,385.28 and 355.94 per 100,000 people, respectively. This suggests a significant unmet need for approximately 49 million surgical procedures across the country. Orthostatic hypotension (OH) and orthostatic intolerance (OI) are prevalent post-operative issues during early mobilization, with a prevalence of 42–50%, according to several prospective studies of major surgery.

Orthostatic hypotension, also known as postural hypotension, is defined as a sudden drop in blood pressure that occurs upon standing from a sitting or supine position. This condition significantly impacts quality of life and increases the risk of falls, cardiovascular disease, dementia, depression, and mortality. Clinically, orthostatic hypotension is defined as a sustained drop in systolic blood pressure (SBP) of at least 20 mm Hg or diastolic blood pressure of 10 mm Hg within 3 minutes of standing after being supine for at least 5 minutes or positioned at a 60° angle on a tilt table. This sudden drop in blood pressure is typically caused by autonomic reflex failure, volume depletion, cardiovascular disease, neuropathy, or adverse medication effects.

The non-pharmacologic strategy aims to minimize heat, postprandial induced vasodilation, postural venous pooling and maximize blood volume. Promoting physical conditioning, by decreasing peripheral capacitance and increasing total peripheral resistance. Leg Maneuver Exercises that primarily involve leg elevation, leg crossing, thigh muscle contraction, are used in conjunction with the majority of non-pharmacologic measures to increase venous return. As the primary member of the healthcare team who works with surgical patients after surgery, nurses are in a unique position to keep an eye out for orthostatic hypotension (OH) symptoms and know about many non-pharmacological ways to improve patients' physical conditions. By identifying these people for orthostatic hypotension (OH), it will be easier to diagnose and treat them early, improving patient safety, decreasing hospital stays and allowing patients to resume their regular activities. Determining the impact of Leg Maneuver Exercises (leg elevation, leg crossing, thigh muscle contraction) on orthostatic hypotension (OH) in surgical patients after surgery is the goal of the current study.

METHOD:

Study Design: A Quasi experimental non-randomized control group design.

Research approach: The research methodology adopted for the study employed a quantitative research approach.

Setting: Selected hospitals.

Sampling technique: Non probability, purposive sampling technique.

Population: Postoperative patient with orthostatic hypotension admitted at selected hospitals.

Study Protocol: Before the data collection, consent was taken from the participants. The pre-test was conducted before the implementation of the intervention (Leg maneuver Exercises). Post intervention on orthostatic hypotension among post-operative patients assessed. The data was collected from 05/12/2025 to 05/01/2026.

Data collection

Section A – It consists of two parts, i.e.

Part I - Semi-structured Interviewing Questionnaire will be prepared by the investigator which includes questions regarding demographic variables: Age, Gender, Education, Health Habits, History of Health Promotion and Activities.

Part II - Semi-structured Interviewing Questionnaire will be prepared by the investigator which includes questions regarding clinical Profile: Pre-Existing Conditions, History of Orthostatic Hypotension, Medication, Duration of Illness, History of Present Surgical Intervention, Type of Anaesthesia Used.

Section B - This consist of finalized tool that is Orthostatic Hypotension Risk Assessments Scale (OHRAS). Is a used the level of orthostatic hypotension symptoms experienced by a patient. It is a subjective measure, where the patient rates their perceives symptoms on a scale from 6 to 30, with 6 bring no symptoms and 30 maximum symptoms of orthostatic hypotension. Further, ask the patients to describe the difficulty of mobilization after abdominal surgery and described level of orthostatic hypotension grading with score key and score grading between 6 to 30 i.e., no evidence of orthostatic hypotension symptoms, mild symptoms, moderate symptoms, maximums symptoms.

Method of Data Collection

1. Approval from the research committee members and written permission from the head of the institution to conduct study was obtained.
2. Purpose of the research was explained to the participants.
3. Informed consent (written) was explained to the participants.
4. Formal permission was obtained from the concerned authority.
5. Subjects were taken from the selected hospitals using non-probability convenient sampling technique.
6. The investigator introduced themselves and informed the samples about the nature of the study to ensure better co-operation during the data collection. Objectives of the study and confidentiality of the data was discussed.
7. The data gathering process began from 06/12/2025 to 02/02/2026
8. Each subject was given a prepared tool containing
 - Section A – Consent form.
 - Section B - Tool for demographic variables and clinical profile.

- Section C – Orthostatic Hypotension Risk Assessments Scale (OHRAS).
9. Assessed hemodynamic parameter (blood pressure and heart rate) with the use of pretest.
 10. Leg maneuver exercises were provided to the orthostatic hypotension patients.
 11. Post-test were collected on the day of five after intervention.

Statistical Methods

Descriptive Statistics: Frequency and percentage distribution were used to describe demographic variables. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyse the pre-test and post-test.

Inferential statistics: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of Leg maneuver exercises on orthostatic hypotension among postoperative patients. Fisher's exact test for association between orthostatic hypotension and selected demographic variables.

Data Analysis:

Sample size: For this study, sample size consisted of approximately 30 participants.

Eligibility criteria:

Inclusion criteria - Patients who are

underwent general abdominal surgeries.

Age group of 18 to above 60 years.

having post-operative orthostatic hypotension risk assessment scale score above 6.

Willing to participate in the study.

Able to understand English, Marathi and Hindi language.

Exclusion criteria- Patients who are

On treatment of hypotension.

critically ill.

Having neurological or vascular disorders.

Withdrawal criteria: Sample can withdraw from research at any point of time during the data collection.

RESULTS:

Finding related to demographic characteristics of the patients with orthostatic hypotension

Age

- In experimental group, 20% of the post-operative patients belong to age of 18-30 years, 40% of them belongs to age of 31-40 years, 20% of them belongs to age of 41-50 years and 20% of them belongs to age of 51-60 years.
- In control group, 20% of the post-operative patients belong to age of 18-30 years, 26.7% of them belongs to age of 31-40 years, 20% of them belongs to age of 41-50 years, 20% of them belongs to age of 51-60 years and 13.3% of them belongs to age of above 60 years.

Gender

- In experimental group, 66.7% of them were males and 33.3% of them were females.
- In control group, 73.3% of them were males and 26.7% of them were females.

Educational status

- In experimental group, 6.7% of them did not have formal education, 26.7% of them had primary education, 33.3% of them had secondary and higher secondary education and 33.3% of them had graduation and post-graduation.
- In control group, 20% of them did not have formal education, 40% of them had primary education, 13.3% of them had secondary and higher secondary education and 26.7% of them had graduation and post-graduation.

Health habit

- In experimental group, 60% of them did not have any habit, 13.3% of them had habit of tobacco chewing, 13.3% of them had habit of cigarette smoking and 13.3% of them were alcoholic.

- In control group, 40% of them did not have any habit, 20% of them had habit of tobacco chewing, 33.3% of them had habit of cigarette smoking and 6.7% of them were alcoholic.

Health promotion activities

- In experimental group, 13.3% of them had yoga, 33.3% of them had brisk walking and 53.3% of them did not have history of health promotion activities.
- In control group, 60% of them had brisk walking and 40% of them did not have history of health promotion activities.

Finding related to clinical characteristics of the patients with orthostatic hypotension

Pre-existing condition

- In experimental group, 26.7% of the post-operative patients had hypertension, 20% of them had diabetes and 53.3% of them did not have any pre-existing condition.
- In control group, 33.3% of the post-operative patients had hypertension, 13.3% of them had diabetes and 53.3% of them did not have any pre-existing condition.

History of orthostatic hypotension

- None of them in experimental and control group had history of orthostatic hypotension.

Medication

- In experimental group, 20% of them had Antihypertensive agents, 26.7% of them had Diuretic medication and 53.3% of them had Opioid medication.
- In control group, 33.3% of them had Antihypertensive agents, 20% of them had Diuretic medication and 46.7% of them had Opioid medication.

Duration of illness

- In experimental and control group, 60% of them had illness for less than 1 month, and 40% of them had illness for 1 to 6 months.

Type of surgery undergone

- In experimental group, 40% of them had Abdominal wall/hernia surgeries, 26.7% of them had lower abdominal surgeries and 33.3% of them had upper abdominal surgeries.
- In control group, 40% of them had Abdominal wall/hernia surgeries, 33.3% of them had lower abdominal surgeries and 26.7% of them had upper abdominal surgeries.

Type of anaesthesia used

- In experimental group, 86.7% of them had general anaesthesia and 13.3% of them had spinal anaesthesia.
- In control group, 53.3% of them had general anaesthesia and 46.7% of them had spinal anaesthesia.

Analysis of data related to orthostatic hypotension among post-operative patients before implementing leg Maneuver exercises among the post-operative patients admitted at selected hospitals.

Table 1: Orthostatic hypotension among post-operative patients before implementing leg Maneuver exercises among the post-operative patients admitted at selected hospitals.

n=30

Orthostatic hypotension	Experimental		Control	
	Pretest		Pretest	
	Freq	%	Freq	%
Nothing at all	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Mild	0	0.0%	1	6.7%
Moderate	0	0.0%	4	26.7%
Severe	9	60.0%	10	66.7%
Maximum	6	40.0%	0	0.0%

In experimental group, 60% of the post-operative patients had severe Orthostatic hypotension and 40% of them had maximum Orthostatic hypotension. In control group, 6.7% of the post-operative patients had mild Orthostatic hypotension, 26.7% of them had moderate orthostatic hypotension and 66.7% of them had severe Orthostatic hypotension.

n=30

Fig.No.1: Bar diagram showing the percentage- wise distribution of pre-test orthostatic hypotension in experimental and control groups.

Analysis of data related to the orthostatic hypotension among post-operative patients after implementing leg Maneuver exercises.

Table 2: Orthostatic hypotension among post-operative patients after implementing leg Maneuver exercises.

n=30

Orthostatic hypotension	Experimental				Control			
	Pre-test		Post-test		Pre-test		Post-test	
	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%	Freq	%
Nothing at all	0	0.0%	12	80.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Mild	0	0.0%	3	20.0%	1	6.7%	2	13.3%
Moderate	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	4	26.7%	11	73.3%
Severe	9	60.0%	0	0.0%	10	66.7%	2	13.3%
Maximum	6	40.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%

n=30

Fig.No.2: Bar diagram showing the percentage - wise distribution of pre-test and post-test orthostatic hypotension in experimental and control group.

In experimental group, in pretest, 60% of the post-operative patients had severe Orthostatic hypotension and 40% of them had maximum Orthostatic hypotension. In post-test, 80% of the post-operative patients did not have orthostatic hypotension and 20% of them had mild Orthostatic hypotension. In control group, in pretest, 6.7% of the post-operative patients had mild Orthostatic hypotension, 26.7% of them had moderate orthostatic hypotension and 66.7% of them had severe Orthostatic hypotension. In post-test, 13.3% of the post-operative patients had mild Orthostatic hypotension, 73.3% of them had moderate orthostatic hypotension and 13.3% of them had severe Orthostatic hypotension. This indicates that there is remarkable improvement in Orthostatic hypotension among post-operative patients.

Table 3: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of Leg maneuverer Exercises on Orthostatic Hypotension among post-operative patients.

n=30

	Mean	SD	t-test	df	p-value
Pre-test	23.1	3.3	21.1	14	0.000
Post-test	6.5	1.0			

n=30

Fig.No.3: Bar diagram showing the distribution of average orthostatic hypotension score among post-operative patients in pre-test and post-test in experimental group.

Researcher applied paired t-test for the effectiveness of Leg Maneuver Exercises on Orthostatic Hypotension among post-operative patients. Average Orthostatic Hypotension score among post-operative patients was 23.1 which reduced to 6.5 in post-test. t-value for this test was 21.1 with 14 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average Orthostatic Hypotension score in post-test was significantly less than that in pretest. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are significantly effective in reducing the Orthostatic Hypotension among post-operative patients.

Table 4: Two sample t-test for the effectiveness of Leg maneuver Exercises on Orthostatic Hypotension among post-operative patients

n=30

Group	Mean	SD	t-test	df	p-value
Experimental	16.6	3.0	15.1	28	0.000
Control	5.3	3.4			

Researcher applied two sample t-test for the effectiveness of Leg maneuver Exercises on Orthostatic Hypotension among post-operative patients. Average reduction in Orthostatic Hypotension score among post-operative patients in experimental group was 16.6 which was to 5.3 in control group. t-value for this test was 15.1 with 28 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average reduction in Orthostatic Hypotension score in experimental group was significantly more than that in control group. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are significantly effective in reducing the Orthostatic Hypotension among post-operative patients.

n=30

Fig.No.4: Bar diagram showing the percentage - wise distribution of average reduction in orthostatic hypotension score among post-operative in experimental and control group

Table 5: Paired t-test for the effectiveness of Leg maneuverer Exercises on hemodynamic parameter (blood pressure and heart rate) among post-operative patients.

n=30

Parameter	Position	Test	Mean	SD	t-test	df	p-value
SBP	Supine/Sitting within 5 min	Pretest	119.9	6.1	0.43	14	0.338
		Post-test	120.7	3.7			
	Standing within 1 min	Pretest	107.0	7.0	2.58	14	0.011
		Post-test	113.1	6.8			
	Standing within 3 min	Pretest	90.4	1.4	47.45	14	0.000
		Post-test	119.3	1.9			
DBP	Supine/Sitting within 5 min	Pretest	74.1	4.6	0.71	14	0.244
		Post-test	75.3	3.8			
	Standing within 1 min	Pretest	67.5	5.6	3.80	14	0.001
		Post-test	73.5	3.5			
	Standing within 3 min	Pretest	60.2	2.1	16.48	14	0.000
		Post-test	75.2	3.7			
HR	Supine/Sitting within 5 min	Pretest	73.1	3.1	0.44	14	0.334
		Post-test	73.7	3.4			
	Standing within 1 min	Pretest	86.7	3.9	4.91	14	0.000
		Post-test	77.6	4.9			
	Standing within 3 min	Pretest	106.6	3.8	24.66	14	0.000
		Post-test	81.5	5.7			

Researcher applied paired t-test for the effectiveness of Leg Maneuver Exercises on vital parameters (SBP, DBP and HR) among post-operative patients. Average systolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 5 min among post-operative patients was 119.9 which was to 120.7 in post-test. T-value for this test was 0.43 with 14 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was large (greater than 0.05), there is no evidence against null hypothesis. Average systolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 5 min in post-test was not significantly more than that in pretest. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are not significantly effective on systolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 5 min among post-operative patients. Average systolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 1 min among post-operative patients was 107 which was to 113.1 in post-test. T-value for this test was 2.58 with 14 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), null hypothesis is rejected. Average systolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 1 min in post-test was significantly more than that in pretest. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are significantly effective on systolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 1 min among post-operative patients. Average systolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 3 min among post-operative patients was 90.4 which was to 119.3 in post-test. T-value for this test was 47.45 with 14 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), null hypothesis is rejected. Average systolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 3 min in post-test was significantly more than that in pretest. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are significantly effective on systolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 3 min among post-operative patients.

Average diastolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 5 min among post-operative patients was 74.1 which was to 75.3 in post-test. T-value for this test was 0.71 with 14 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was large (greater than 0.05), there is no evidence against null hypothesis. Average diastolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 5 min in post-test was not significantly more than that in pretest. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are not significantly effective on diastolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 5 min among post-operative patients. Average diastolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 1 min among post-operative patients was 67.5 which was to 73.5 in post-test. T-value for this test was 3.8 with 14 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), null hypothesis is rejected. Average diastolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 1 min in post-test was significantly more than that in pretest. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are significantly effective on diastolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 1 min among post-operative patients. Average diastolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 3 min among post-operative patients was 60.2 which was to 75.2 in post-test. T-value for this test was 0.44 with 14 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), null hypothesis is rejected. Average diastolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 3 min in post-test was significantly more than that in pretest. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are significantly effective on diastolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 3 min among post-operative patients.

Average heart rate in Supine/Sitting within 5 min among post-operative patients was 73.1 which was to 73.7 in post-test. t-value for this test was 0.44 with 14 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was large (greater than 0.05), there is no evidence against null hypothesis. Average heart rate in Supine/Sitting within 5 min in post-test was not significantly more than that in pretest. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are not significantly effective on heart rate in Supine/Sitting within 5 min among post-operative patients. Average heart rate in Supine/Sitting within 1 min among post-operative patients was 86.7 which was to 77.6 in post-test. t-value for this test was 4.91 with 14 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), null hypothesis is rejected. Average heart rate in Supine/Sitting within 1 min in post-test was significantly less than that in pretest. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are significantly effective on heart rate in Supine/Sitting within 1 min among post-operative patients. Average heart rate in Supine/Sitting within 3 min among post-operative patients was 106.6 which was to 81.5 in post-test. t-value for this test was 24.66 with 14 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), null hypothesis is rejected. Average heart rate in Supine/Sitting within 3 min in post-test was significantly less than that in pretest. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are significantly effective on heart rate in Supine/Sitting within 3 min among post-operative patients.

n=30

Fig.No.5: Bar diagram showing the distribution of average orthostatic hypotension score among post-operative patients in pre-test and post-test in experimental group

n=30

Fig.No.6: Bar diagram showing the distribution of average diastolic blood pressure among post-operative patients in experimental group in pre-test and post-test

n=30

Fig.No.7: Bar diagram showing the distribution of average heart rate among post operative patients in experimental group in pre-test and post-test

Table 6: Two sample t-test for the comparison of change in hemodynamic parameters among post-operative patients in experimental and control group

n=30

Parameter	Position	Test	Mean	SD	t-test	df	p-value
SBP	Supine/Sitting within 5 min	Experimental	0.73	6.65	0.31	28	0.380
		Control	0.20	0.56			
	Standing within 1 min	Experimental	6.07	9.10	1.67	28	0.053
		Control	1.87	3.40			
	Standing within 3 min	Experimental	28.87	2.36	26.38	28	0.000
		Control	5.93	2.40			
DBP	Supine/Sitting within 5 min	Experimental	1.20	6.52	0.55	28	0.293
		Control	0.27	0.59			
	Standing within 1 min	Experimental	6.00	6.12	2.07	28	0.024
		Control	2.60	1.72			
	Standing within 3 min	Experimental	15.00	3.53	10.16	28	0.000
		Control	4.33	2.02			
HR	Supine/Sitting within 5 min	Experimental	-0.60	5.30	0.82	28	0.210
		Control	0.53	0.83			
	Standing within 1 min	Experimental	9.07	7.15	3.29	28	0.001
		Control	2.87	1.51			
	Standing within 3 min	Experimental	25.07	3.94	11.48	28	0.000
		Control	7.67	4.35			

Researcher applied two sample t-test for the comparison of change in vital parameters among post-operative patients in experimental and control group. Average increase in systolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 5 min among post-operative

patients in experimental group was 0.73 which was 0.2 in control group. T-value for this test was 0.31 with 28 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was large (greater than 0.05), there is no evidence against null hypothesis. Average increase in systolic blood pressure in experimental group was not significantly more than that in control group. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are not significantly effective in increasing the systolic blood pressure among post-operative patients. Average increase in systolic blood pressure in Standing within 1 min among post-operative patients in experimental group was 6.07 which was 1.87 in control group. T-value for this test was 1.67 with 28 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was large (greater than 0.05), there is no evidence against null hypothesis. Average increase systolic blood pressure in Standing within 1 min in experimental group was not significantly more than that in control group. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are not significantly effective in increasing the systolic blood pressure in Standing within 1 min among post-operative patients. Average increase in systolic blood pressure in Standing within 3 min among post-operative patients in experimental group was 28.87 which was 5.93 in control group. T-value for this test was 26.38 with 28 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average increase systolic blood pressure in Standing within 3 min in experimental group was significantly more than that in control group. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are significantly effective in increasing the systolic blood pressure in Standing within 3 min among post-operative patients.

Average increase in diastolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 5 min among post-operative patients in experimental group was 1.20 which was 0.27 in control group. T-value for this test was 0.55 with 28 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was large (greater than 0.05), there is no evidence against null hypothesis. Average increase in diastolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 5 min in experimental group was not significantly more than that in control group. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are not significantly effective in increasing the diastolic blood pressure in Supine/Sitting within 5 min among post-operative patients. Average increase in diastolic blood pressure in Standing within 1 min among post-operative patients in experimental group was 6 which was 2.6 in control group. T-value for this test was 2.07 with 28 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average increase diastolic blood pressure in Standing within 1 min in experimental group was significantly more than that in control group. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are significantly effective in increasing the diastolic blood pressure in Standing within 1 min among post-operative patients. Average increase in diastolic blood pressure in Standing within 3 min among post-operative patients in experimental group was 15 which was 4.33 in control group. T-value for this test was 10.16 with 28 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average increase diastolic blood pressure in Standing within 3 min in experimental group was significantly more than that in control group. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are significantly effective in increasing the diastolic blood pressure in Standing within 3 min among post-operative patients.

Average reduction in heart rate in Supine/Sitting within 5 min among post-operative patients in experimental group was -0.6 which was 0.53 in control group. T-value for this test was 0.82 with 28 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was large (greater than 0.05), there is no evidence against null hypothesis. Average change in heart rate in Supine/Sitting within 5 min in experimental group was not significantly more than that in control group. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are not significantly effective in reducing the heart rate in Supine/Sitting within 5 min among post-operative patients. Average reduction in heart rate in Standing within 1 min among post-operative patients in experimental group was 9.07 which was 2.87 in control group. T-value for this test was 3.29 with 28 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average reduction heart rate in Standing within 1 min in experimental group was significantly more than that in control group. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are significantly effective in reducing the heart rate in Standing within 1 min among post-operative patients. Average reduction in heart rate in Standing within 1 min among post-operative patients in experimental group was 25.07 which was 7.67 in control group. T-value for this test was 11.48 with 28 degrees of freedom. Corresponding p-value was small (less than 0.05), the null hypothesis is rejected. Average reduction heart rate in Standing within 1 min in experimental group was significantly more than that in control group. It is evident that the Leg maneuver exercises are significantly effective in reducing the heart rate in Standing within 1 min among post-operative patients.

n=30

Fig.No.8: Bar diagram showing the distribution of average change in systolic blood pressure among post-operative patients in experimental group and control group.

n=30

Fig.No.9: Bar diagram showing the distribution of average changes in diastolic blood pressure among post-operative patients in experimental group and control group.

Fig.No.10: Bar diagram showing the distribution of average changes in heart rate among post-operative patients in experimental group and control group.

Analysis of data related to association between Orthostatic Hypotension and selected demographic variables

Fisher’s exact test for the association between Orthostatic Hypotension and selected demographic variables

Fishers’s exact test shows the association between orthostatic hypotension and selected demographic variables among post-operative patients, analyzed using Fisher’s exact test at a significance level of $p < 0.05$. The findings revealed a statistically significant association between age and orthostatic hypotension ($p = 0.015$), indicating that the severity of orthostatic hypotension varied significantly across different age groups. A statistically significant association was also observed between history of health promotion activities and orthostatic hypotension ($p = 0.013$), suggesting that engagement in health promotion activities influenced the severity of orthostatic hypotension. However, no statistically significant association was found between orthostatic hypotension and gender ($p = 0.288$), educational status ($p = 0.095$), or health habits ($p = 0.255$). Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected for age and history of health promotion activities and accepted for gender, education, and health habits.

RECOMMENDATIONS:

- Based on the present study, the investigator suggested the following recommendations:
- A similar study may be replicated on larger samples to enhance generalizability of the findings.
- The study can be replicated in different hospital settings.
- The study can be replicated by changing the type of post-operative patients or surgical procedures.
- An experimental study can be conducted using different non-pharmacological interventions for orthostatic hypotension.
- A similar study can be conducted using different research designs and longer follow-up periods.
- Comparative studies can be conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of leg maneuver exercises with other preventive strategies.

ABBRIATION:

SBP: Systolic Blood Pressure

DBP: Diastolic Blood Pressure

OH: Orthostatic Hypotension

OI: Orthostatic Intolerance

OHRAS: Orthostatic Hypotension Risk Assessment Scale

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